

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Oxo-Molybdenum (V) Complexes with Nitrogen-Donor Ligands

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In continuation of the previous work on molybdenum (v)^{1,2}, a few more molybdenum (v) complexes have been characterised. These complexes are highly coloured and quite stable in air. All the complexes are diamagnetic indicating spin-pairing due to polymerisation in the system.

Using $(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{MoOCl}_6)$ as the source of molybdenum (v) and by varying different solvents and reaction conditions, several complexes with Pyridine 2-aldoxime (PADH); 2-Benzoyl pyridine (BpyH); Salicyl hydrazide (SHDH); Benzoyl hydrazide (BHDH); *o*-Chloro benzoyl hydrazide (*cl*-BHDH); Benzohydroxamic acid (BH_2); *o* and *p*-Chloro benzohydroxamic acid (*o* and *p*-Chloro BH_2); *p*-Anisyl hydroxamic acid (*p*- AH_2 hydrox) and Quinoline 8-hydroxamic acid ($\text{Q}^8\text{H}_2\text{hydrox}$)₂ have been isolated and characterised by elemental analysis (Table I). Unfortunately, all the complexes are insoluble in common solvents. The diffuse reflectance spectra, however, have been taken for some of the representative complexes such as benzohydroxamic acid and benzoyl pyridine following Lee, Griswold and Kleinberg³ in UVISPEK spectrophotometer. The benzohydroxamic acid complex provides bands at around 24,000 cm^{-1} ; 19,600 cm^{-1} ; and 14,000 cm^{-1} and represent transitions $\text{dxy} \rightarrow \text{dz}^2$; $\text{dxy} \rightarrow \text{dx}^2 - \text{y}^2$ and $\text{dxy} \rightarrow \text{dxz}$, dyz respectively. But two d-d transitions are observed ($\text{dxy} \rightarrow \text{dz}^2$ and $\text{dxy} \rightarrow \text{dxz}$, dyz) with benzoyl pyridine complex. The bands due to $\text{dxy} \rightarrow \text{dx}^2 - \text{y}^2$ is not well resolved. However the band positions are characteristic of oxo-molybdenum (v) complex. The determination of oxidation states in hydroxamic acid complexes did not quite materialise. The prolonged shaking of the complexes with 12 N HCl at ordinary temperature provides a green colour, which is characteristic of oxomolybdenum (v)⁴. However the visible spectral band positions have little doubt as to quinquevalence of molybdenum in the complexes.

Work is now in progress with a variety of nitrogen-donor ligands. A full description of the results including preparation, characterisation, visible spectra, magnetic moments, X-ray, I.R., TG, DTG, DTA studies will be communicated in due course.

1. R. L. Dutta and B. Chatterjee, *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 729; 1967, **44**, 758, 1967, **44**, 685,
2. Idem, *ibid*, under publication.
3. R. H. Lee, G. Griswold and J. Kleinberg, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 1278.
4. M. Larson and F. Moore, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 881.

TABLE I

Analysis and Physical properties of the Oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes.

Complex	Colour	Analytical data	
		Found(%)	Required(%)
Type—A.			
1. [MoO ₂ Cl (PADH)]	Orange	Mo :34.4	33.8
		N :10.0	9.9
		Cl :12.1	12.5
2. [MoO ₂ Cl (BpyH)]	Maroon	Mo :28.0	27.7
		N : 4.3	4.04
		Cl :10.6	10.2
3. [MoO ₂ Cl (BHDH)]	Pale orange	Mo :32.5	32.06
		N :10.0	9.35
		Cl :12.2	11.85
4. [MoO ₂ Cl (SHDH)]	Maroon	Mo :30.7	30.4
		N : 9.26	8.9
		Cl : 11.8	11.2
5. [MoO ₂ Cl (CL-BHDH)]	Pale orange	Mo : 28.2	28.7
		N : 9.0	8.4
		Cl :11.0	10.6
Type—B.			
6. [MoO(OH) (BH) ₂]	Green	Mo :24.2 N : 6.8	24.0 7.0
7. [MoO(OH)(<i>o</i> -ChloroBH) ₂]	Do	Mo :20.35 N : 5.8	20.35 5.9
8. [MoO(OH)(<i>p</i> -ChloroBH) ₂]	Do	Mo :20.4 N : 5.8	20.4 5.9
9. [MoO (OH) (<i>p</i> -AH hydrox) ₂]	Do	Mo :20.9 N : 6.1	20.8 6.08
10. [MoO(OH)(Q'H hydrox) ₂]	Do	Mo :19.3 N : 5.7	19.12 5.57
11. [MoO (OH) (CH) ₂]	Orange	Mo :23.0 N : 6.0	22.8 6.08

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